

LIVED EXPERIENCES OF TERTIARY PHYSICAL EDUCATORS IN *QUARANTEACHING*

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Abstract

The inclusion of Physical Education in the curriculum in this new normal in education, and with the mandate on the adoption of flexible learning in the tertiary level caused by the Covid19 pandemic forced Physical Educators to do *quaranteaching* or teaching in the quarantine. The study described the lived experiences of Physical Education teachers in the *quaranteaching* of Physical Education utilizing Edmund Husserl Phenomenological Qualitative research design. It was participated by the seven Physical Education teachers from the two state universities in Cebu, Philippines and was able to achieve data saturation. Anchored to Colaizzi's phenomenological approach and guided by different philosophies, data were analyzed and presented into two prong clustering. Results yielded that tertiary Physical Education teachers experienced difficulties and innovations in terms of teaching the course, assessment, monitoring, and giving feedback to students, dealing with the internet and technology, and handling physical and cognitive situations. It was recommended to expose Tertiary Physical Education teachers in pedagogical and technological trainings and seminar-workshops especially in the utilization of different learning platforms that will help them improve their teaching pedagogies and digitalness in teaching Physical Education in the new normal.

Key Words: *Lived Experiences; Tertiary Physical Educators; Quaranteaching*

INTRODUCTION

The novel coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) did not exempt anyone. All sectors of the society were affected, including education. According to Education International (2020), the pandemic led to an education crisis where no one was prepared. When the quarantine was imposed, everyone was advised to stay at home and observe social distancing to contain the spread of the virus (WHO, 2020). Everyone was ordered to follow the protocols and guidelines set by the Covid19 Inter Agency Task Force (IATF). All educational institutions, public and private are temporarily close in attempt to contain the spread of the virus.

The pandemic seriously gave impact to all stakeholders of the

academe worldwide (Mailizar et al., 2020 cited in Adnan and Anwar, 2020).

As of December 2020, UNESCO recorded that the closure of various institutions due to the Covid19 pandemic affected a total of 317, 816, 657 learners all over the globe, which included enrolled students in the preprimary, primary, lower-secondary, upper secondary, as well as students in the tertiary educational levels.

Furthermore, Philippine educational institutions were presented with surmounting challenges in its system of planning, implementation, and assessment (Toquero, 2020). Recently, the Philippines had recorded 28, 451, 212 enrolled Filipino students that were affected by this pandemic (UNESCO, 2020). This was due to the strict suspension of mass gatherings,

school activities and face-to-face or inperson classes, which led to the adoption of flexible learning strategy or mode in delivery instruction (CHED Covid19 Advisory No.7). The implementation of flexible learning strategy aimed to mitigate the immediate impact of school closures, particularly for more vulnerable and disadvantaged communities, and to facilitate the continuity of education for all through *quaranteaching* (UNESCO, 2020).

“*Quaranteaching*” or teaching in the quarantine as defined by Pace & Pettie (2020) referred to the process of delivering instructions in the middle of community quarantine, which no physical and direct interaction happened between the teachers and the learners. The teaching-learning process happened in the virtual classroom and other learning platforms. This *quaranteaching* had thrust educators into uncharted territory. Although the curriculum remains challenging, exploratory, integrative, and relevant, some educational institutions deliver instructions through virtual classroom and other learning management system (NMSA, 2010 cited in Pace, et al., 2020).

This rapid transformation was linked to various obstacles and challenges at this point (Crawford et al., 2020 cited in Adnan et al., 2020). Many best practice approaches used in traditional classroom settings can be effectively applied in the virtual environment; yet how they were applied to online teaching and learning differs (Goodyear et al., 2001 cited in Pace, et al., 2020). So, teachers perhaps were deciding to reset, and discarded all the effective practices they currently used in face-to-face classes.

In this century, instead of adhering to traditional modes of instruction both parties, the teachers and learners were expected to reverse the traditional classroom-based learning and include new technology while presenting and sharing content knowledge. This *quaranteaching* challenged teachers and educators the most, though the traditional class instruction was restricted, but learning would not be stopped, and duties of teachers continued. Teaching with no face-to-face interaction for the first time had precarious process especially in the delivery of the learning contents that brought a big challenge to the educators like the tertiary physical educators.

Tertiary Physical Educators were the teachers handling Physical Education (PE) courses in the tertiary level. They were responsible in giving the students a practical knowledge on varied activities which prominence on pleasure and fitness thru a certain activity which can be played and enjoyed throughout lifetime, it included development of the vital skills, principles of the activity, background of the activities and games, regulations, scoring, strategies, courtesies, and general safety precautions. Physical educators served as facilitators towards achieving the PE tertiary program outcomes-having an active and healthy living and advocacy and promotion of physical activities (Policies & Guidelines on the Implementation of Tertiary PE Programs).

The inclusion of PE courses in the Philippine curriculum had been talk of the town recently. It was when Senator Gatchalian, chairman of the Senate Committee on Basic Education, Arts, and Culture proposed that only the basic subjects like English, Math and Science will be retained in this new

normal in education. Subjects like PE would not be included for a while considering that these are skill-related subjects, and it needs proper scaffolding from teachers or experts.

On the other hand, various fitness enthusiasts and policy makers opposed this proposal. Physical wellbeing was something we cannot simply set aside, especially in this time of Covid-19 pandemic. One needed to keep promoting PE and regular exercise among our children. (Cayetano, 2020). Being physically active this time of pandemic can strengthen our Immune System, through this we could combat the virus (DOH, 2020 report). Cayetano added that what matters most was PE was not disregarded, and the need to teach children the importance of taking care of their health while at home. After all, article 14 section 19 of the Philippine 1987 Constitution was an evident that PE should be in the frontline. For through this, we would be able to produce healthy and alert citizenry (Official Gazette of the Philippine Constitution).

The retainment of Physical Education as one of the core subjects in the curriculum in this new normal in education challenged Physical Educators the most especially on delivering quality Physical Education utilizing these new modalities of learning. It was a big question on how the teaching-learning process prospered in terms of instruction, assessment, application, feedbacking and monitoring progress without breaking the protocols set by the government and continue in molding and producing healthy and alert Filipino citizens. How can one assure that in the middle of quarantine learning and development of students is still a priority?

Despite the effects of the pandemic to the education sector, it was important that people still lived with an active and healthy lifestyle and stay focused on their life-long fitness and wellness through the quaranteaching of Physical Education. But up to what extent teachers in the country, like Physical Education teachers became prepared when another crisis comes? How can Physical Education teachers easily intervene and stay committed on achieving the program outcomes and instilling the importance of fitness and wellness? These initiated the researcher to conduct a study about quaranteaching in PE.

This study aimed to describe the lived experiences of Tertiary Physical Education teachers in teaching Physical Education courses during the quarantine. There was a need to know their lived experiences because this helped everyone better understand their situation in the pandemic when it came to delivering instructions with no direct face to face interaction. Furthermore, the study described their experiences in teaching for this gave us information on the things to be improved in the teaching-learning process of Physical Education and on the modalities of learning in this new normal in education. The study served as the bases in implementing programs, trainings and seminarworkshops that improved the *quaranteaching* experiences of teachers of Tertiary Physical Educators.

Philosophical Stance

The researcher was committed to conduct study that had a big contribution to the body of knowledge and helped in improving the country's educational system. The study served as the bridge in unlocking the experiences of the participants in trying times. With the

researcher's current situation, this led him in examining issues that the researcher also experienced during the pandemic. The researcher's authentic experiences yielded gaps that were not giving enough interventions and attention. These viewpoints of the researcher made him sensitive to the different assumptions that served his guidance towards understanding the authenticity of the study. The study anchored to the different beliefs and assumptions which included the ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological assumptions.

Ontological Assumption.

The reality was subjective and there was no single reality. There were multiple realities depending on the individual's experiences, beliefs, opinions, and perspectives. The reality was stocked in one's minds and knowing what real was when we heard and saw it verbally. In the study, this aimed to describe the lived experiences of Physical Education teachers in teaching PE during the quarantine, specifically this included the process of the teaching-learning process, the challenges they encountered, the opportunities they perceived and the essential qualities of an effective teacher as they teach in these new modalities of learning. Through this study, teachers were given the chance to share their insights, their beliefs, and opinions on certain phenomena. The researcher supported the idea that through direct experiences, realities existed and through different perspectives, multiple realities came out. By simply letting them share and speak up was an avenue of constructing realities.

Epistemological Assumption.

Knowing the truth and real knowledge depended on how a person experienced thing. Since the researcher himself was a Physical Education instructor teaching in the quarantine, this believed that this established relationship in the phenomena being studied. In assuring authentic truth would come out, the three broad types of knowledge under epistemology, namely, factual knowledge, practical knowledge and knowledge of people and places was used as guides. In the study, the researcher relied on the vignette or lines of the participants which served as the evidence. Words coming from the Physical Education instructors about their lived experiences in quaranteaching were the truth and the real knowledge and researcher acted as an "insider" only. *Axiological Assumption.*

The main aim of this study was to describe the lived experiences of tertiary Physical Education teachers in teaching Physical Education courses in the quarantine. Through this, lived experiences of Physical Educators in quaranteaching were giving meanings. Their world was discovered, and this gave them a lot of opportunities. Values that clearly shaped the narrative were clearly discussed by the researchers and the researcher's own interpretation conjunction to the interpretation of the participants. The context of its value was also reflected how this study benefited a lot of people. The Chapter 1 of the manuscript clearly explained the purpose why this study was conducted and how helped a lot of people. This study was beneficial not just to the different stakeholders of the academe but also to the policy makers and different members in the community.

Methodological Assumption.

The researcher believed that conducting a qualitative research was a systematic process and it followed a series of steps. From identifying the gaps, selecting the right method, gathering the necessary data, interpreting data gathered, analyzing the data, and validating the results. Through these, identified gaps were given possible solutions. Moreover, the researcher used Colaizzi's approach of descriptive phenomenology data analysis. Manual coding was used in generating the themes. The researcher followed steps in determining the different themes that yielded in the study. From getting the codes to validating the results, everything was methodological. Before jumping into conclusions, details and specific aspects was reviewed by the researcher. Also, the researcher discussed every detail of the study supporting different literatures. With the researcher's experiences, it was a big help in making the study more comprehensive. Guide questions were being revised and checked by experts, manuscript was being checked by the advisers and entire study undergone research design hearing final oral defense.

METHODOLOGY

The researcher adopted the Descriptive Phenomenological Qualitative research design by Edmund Husserl in conducting the study. Descriptive phenomenology was the best way to capture narrative accounts of participants, which reflected how they expressed, shared, and voiced out their experiences through in-depth interviews (Gagne et al.,2010). Descriptive phenomenology aimed to know what the experiences were and how they were experienced. Through this approach, the world, and experiences of the

Physical Educators in the *quaranteaching* were interpreted and were given meanings.

Seven tertiary PE teachers from the two state universities in Cebu Philippines participated in the study and were selected through purposive snowball sampling. They were selected using these criteria: (a) must be a degree holder of any Physical Education related program in the bachelor/master/doctorate degree, (b) must be a PE teaching faculty staff and teaching Physical Education courses in the identified research locale in Academic Year 2020-2021 and (c) must be teaching Physical Education in quarantine engaging in the new modalities of teaching-learning process. Moreover, with the sampling used, the key informants recommended someone to be invited as one of the key informants of the study knowing that he/she passed the set criteria.

The researcher served as the instrument in the gathering of data. Non-directive interview was utilized with the help of a guide question. Google Meet was the platform used in doing the online interview. First step in the data collection, especially in the data collection of a phenomenological qualitative study was to assure that biases and assumptions of the researcher were avoided. This was avoided through the process of epoche or phenomenological reduction. This included writing down on a journal the pre-conceived biases, assumptions, and beliefs of the researcher. In this way, one assured that authentic truth revealed in the study. Through epoche also, lived experiences of the PE teachers were described without the influence of the researcher's point of view. This stage of the interview process played an important role because

through this, the researcher was reminded on his own biases and was conscious in the line of questioning. This stage of the online interview was where the researcher be reminded that follow up questions and clarifications were based on the key informant's responses not on what the researcher believed in. During the interview all informants were asked the same lead in question "Can you please share to me your experiences in teaching Physical Education in the quarantine?" Right after the interview, data were then transcribed and analyzed through Colaizzi's approach of phenomenological data analysis.

Ethical Consideration

The conduct of the study commenced after the researchers were granted an ethical clearance from the university Research Ethics Committee (REC). Ethical protocols were observed prior and during the data gathering procedure. The researcher gave an informed consent from to the participants. Participation in the study is completely voluntary. Before the interview, the participants were informed that conversation was recorded, and rest assured that the recordings were used for data analysis only. Only the researchers have the access to the recordings. Recordings were saved in the researcher's private disc and were protected by codes. Pseudonyms were used in the entire process of the study to hide the informant's identity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The lived experiences of Tertiary PE teachers in quaranteaching were describe through two prong clustering. Main themes generated in the study were difficulties and innovation in quaranteaching with subthemes in

terms of instruction, assessment, monitoring and feedbacking, internet and technology and physical and cognitive situations.

Theme 1: Difficulties in Quaranteaching

The study revealed that Tertiary PE teachers having a hard in the quaranteaching of Physical Education. The sudden shift to distance learning forced PE teachers to engage in different platforms without enough knowledge and in-depth training on the utilizations of the platform and the teaching of the course with no direct face to face interaction. ***Difficulties in Instruction***

The teaching of Physical Education with no direct contact with the students was one of the problems PE teachers experienced. Physical Education is known to be a skill-based and performance-based course and direct scaffolding from teachers was necessary. But because of the pandemic, this limited teachers from assisting and guiding their students. The nature of the course became a leading problem why PE teachers experienced difficulties in teaching PE in the quarantine One key informant said that:

"I can say that a PE teacher adjusted very much because as we have known PE is for performance. I'm struggling teaching with no face-to-face interaction. I questioned myself how will I address my lesson?"

This statement of the informant proved that teachers questioned themselves on how they were going to teach in the new learning platform. Teaching pedagogy had been a problem in the teaching of PE. This

agreed to the study of O'Brien et al (2020) which found out that pedagogy was one of the weaknesses in the teaching of Physical Education program in countries like England, Finland, Greece, Ireland, and Portugal.

Another informant also shared that:

“So, the experience was really hard because in Physical Education we were more on hands-on. We will show the skill it in front of them. Unlike in the video call we cannot show them.”

This response of one of the informants proved that distance learning in Physical Education had a barrier towards teaching of skill. Teachers could not directly teach and monitor the students since they were separated by screen and was connected only by a certain medium. This result supported the study of Varea & Calvo (2020) which found out that Physical Education pre-service teachers having a difficulty in assembling themselves and in teaching their students since there was no direct contact with the students. Having no proximity towards the students changes a lot in the teaching of Physical Education.

Difficulties in Assessment, Monitoring and Feedbacking

Since informants engaged in a set-up, their way of assessment feedbacking and monitoring also was changed. Informants' experiences changed the way how they assessed or evaluated students. Unlike with the face-to-face classes, teachers could directly assess student's performance might it be in a traditional way or in an authentic way. Teachers shared that assessing, monitoring, and feedbacking students in remote teaching was new. One informant said that:

“The hardest part for me is the checking. My activities are more on videos because we are more in a performance-based, so we need to see that they are doing it like warm-up. I need to see them if they execute this certain drill for sport. I will ask them to take a video. That's the heavy adjustment in our part. You need to have fast-paced in checking.”

The informant shared the importance of facilitating and evaluating students' output. The new normal brought so much burden in the teachers especially that this time students would do individual outputs and teachers must check their outputs. The teacher needed to be fast in checking outputs for efficiency purposes. This situation was a major challenge to the teachers, and it supported the study of Williyanto (2020). According to the researcher, the facilitating the outputs of all students was a crucial goal in online teaching. Teachers must be hardworking enough to check student's output. Another informant also shared that:

“So, my lived experiences it's been hard to teach PE in new normal especially here in the virtual setting because teaching requires close monitoring of students and also monitoring them by, and also giving them hands-on activities.”

The informant expressed how hard teaching Physical Education in the new normal especially in monitoring students and giving activities suited for PE. This supported the study of Varea (2020) which stated that the job of a PE teacher became harder since close

monitoring was lost and this brought another burden in teaching and assessing students.

Difficulties on the Technology and Internet

One of the common challenges of Physical Educators in the teaching of PE in the quarantine was the technology and intermittent internet connectivity. This problem was clearly expressed by the teachers, and it was not just the teachers who experienced this challenge, but also the students. Some students were not capable of online learning because they did not internet network at home. Intermittent internet connectivity was the common challenge of both the teachers and students because this was the medium on delivering instruction. One of the informants said that:

“At first, I struggled in using the Google Classroom and the Google Meet since we don’t have proper training in using it. We had training but not that in depth. I discovered something in the classroom ahead of time.”

The informant shared that they had lack of training in learning the platforms. Majority of teachers shared that they exposed only in pedagogy but not in the utilization of technology. This data supported the phenomenological study of Khanal (2020), in which according to the result of study, teachers underwent trainings, but it was not enough to properly handle online classes. Trainings were more on the features of nature of the platform, but technicalities were not fully inculcated to the teachers. Another also voiced out that:

“In my experience what struggles me the most is the internet connection. For me, I cannot say that I struggle with internet connection more often because I will conduct classes at school. So, I will just connect to the school’s WIFI. So, it’s kind of okay. I feel sad for the students because they will keep on asking if it’s okay if they will leave earlier because they will still go home. They are not in their house; they will go to other places because the internet connection in their place is slow, they need to go to another place to join my class.

The informant emphasized that internet connectivity was such a big problem in an online class. Students who were unfortunate to live in an area where the signal was weak struggled in joining their classes. Location greatly and it affirmed to the result of the study conducted by Nasri et al., (2020) which stated that students living in an area where the technological limitations were massive, experienced difficulties in joining classes or even in accessing the learning platforms

Difficulties on Physical and Cognitive Situations

The sudden shift from face to face to online teaching did not just affect the teachers when it comes to their job and in their pedagogies of teaching. The study also found out Tertiary Physical Education teachers also experienced difficulties when it comes to the physical and cognitive situations. This included the impact of quaranteaching to the health of the teachers at the same of maintaining good student-teacher interaction. One informant shared that:

“My first two weeks in dealing the online classes I am not feeling well because I am not used to just looking at the one corner. Looking at the camera gave me headache. All my body parts are not feeling well. I got fever because of being inactive. I got body pain also.”

This revealed that both students and teachers said negative things on the utilization of the new platform. Moreover, teaching in new learning platform affected the teacher's health especially the physical aspect. This statement affirmed to the study of Tria (2020) which stated that online teaching a major threat in student and teachers' health. So, it was necessary to strengthen research and development of health in the academe.

Another informant also shared that:

“The first challenge that I encountered is my communication to my students. I was challenged on how I will communicate to my student's feelings, how they will feel what I teach.”

The informant emphasized that communicating with students in distance learning was a challenge. It limited the teacher on expressing her feelings towards the students. This statement affirmed to the study of Hebebcı et al (2020), which found out that since in this online class they are separate environment it reduced the duration of their interaction. Furthermore, the informant shared those students from rural area were struggling with their internet connectivity since the signal there was weak. This affirmed to the study of Mercier et al (2020), which revealed that students in

the rural area were most likely experienced intermittent internet connection which were less effective in distance learning.

This COVID19 pandemic changed a lot in the educational system of the country, and it affected the lives of Physical Education teachers (Haverback, 2020). Informants adjusted a lot especially on delivering the lessons and activities in this *quaranteaching*. *Quaranteaching* considered to be an empire constituted by the educators and they were not familiar with its culture and practices (Pace, 2020). Meaning educators entered this set-up without proper orientation and exposure. That was why challenges and difficulties existed as quaranteaching continue to prosper. One of the challenges of this quaranteaching which was highlighted by Pace (2020) was accessibility to technology. Lot of students worldwide did not have access to internet due to financial instability and geographical location. Remote learning was a disadvantage for them especially for those families who belonged to poor families (Garcia & Weiss, 2020). The study also supported the study of Rasmitadila et al., (2020) which stated that remote teaching was challenging especially on the utilization of the platforms and not all students and teachers had access to stable internet connection and had gadgets at home.

To sum up theme number 1 revealed that Tertiary Physical Education teachers experienced difficulties in the new normal. These difficulties were on the giving of instruction, assessing and monitoring students' progress, difficulties on the internet connection and technology used and difficulties when it came to their physical and social aspects.

Theme 2: Innovations in Quaranteaching

The second theme that was clustered in the study revealed how the informants cope up with their difficulties and challenges. The study showed that tertiary Physical Education teachers learned to innovate and adapt this new normal. There were negative feedbacks coming from the teachers about this new set-up of education, but they learned to adjust and cope up with these changes. Informants learned to trust the process and stay optimistic about this set-up. The fact that face-toface classes could not be implemented yet because of the pandemic, teachers learned to accept that this is the new reality.

Innovations in Instruction

Adopting new way teaching was an appropriate way towards delivering quality instruction. Teachers became open to new knowledge that helped them in coping with the problems they experienced especially in the teachinglearning process. Teachers took advantage of the technology to explore and innovate so that they could deliver their lesson or any resources available.

They utilized the technology and the learning platforms to deliver instructions both in synchronous and asynchronous learning. Even in assessments and monitoring student's progress, technology became the way of the teachers. They utilized every resource that they have in order for them to deliver quality Physical Education during this time pandemic. One informant stated that:

“My way of teaching them is that I will give them activities.... I will just send them link of videos or article and I will instruct them

watch and read what I sent to them. On the following day, I will give my feedback and give followups on what they have learned. I will do oral recitation. That's my way.”

The informant revealed that most of the time they utilized asynchronous online learning since majority of the students had intermittent internet connection. The teachers just sent videos or articles and let the students watch and read these depending on their availability. This statement alone supported the study of Nasri et al., (2020) which also found out that teachers did asynchronous online classes since students were experiencing internet difficulties. Another informant also highlighted that:

“So here in teaching PE we integrate technology. So, what do you mean by integrating technology, we use internet to send instructions, to give assignments, ahm to give videos, pictures that would be necessary for them in to have knowledge and to know their topics especially here in PE in a virtual setting. So, we integrated technology sir.”

The informant shared that teacher in the new learning platform integrate technology in teaching. This included giving of instructions, videos, pictures that helped students learn and be familiar with their assigned topics. This contradicted to the results of the study of Williyanto (2020), which found out that less teachers utilized technology due to the status of the students. Majority of them gave worksheets to the students.

Innovations in Assessment, Monitoring and Feedbacking

This distance learning helped PE teachers upgrade their assessments, way of monitoring students and giving feedbacks. To facilitate assessment, feedbacking and monitoring of students, teachers made some innovation and in their pedagogies. From the actual direct demonstration of skills and physical activities, teachers used video-based instruction to show the proper execution of the skills. Some teachers took a video of themselves executing the skills, while others utilized the links on the internet and gave it to their students. Internet played an important role in the teaching of Physical Education during quarantine. The informant emphasized that:

“Yes. Even in giving them examinations. I also have live examinations. Like they can immediately answer, and they will know immediately whether their answer is correct. There was a ranking as well.”

The informant utilized online assessment in this time pandemic, and this supported to the study of Tartavulea et al., (2020) which stated this time of pandemic in the engagement in online assessment increased. Educators learned to embrace the assessment in this new set-up of education. Another informant shared that:

“It’s okay when it comes to discussion, the problem is that I am teaching PE 3, PE 4 and here you need to keep moving. I cannot say that they can see me moving, that’s why I make use of videos. At first, I took a video of myself then

I will send it to them. The problem is it will take time so I just search videos in YouTube, and I will show it to them”

The informants shared that video-based instruction was utilized in order to teach Physical Education in the new normal. These videos were personally made by the teacher and others are taken from the internet like YouTube. This supported the study by conducted by Rasmitadili et al (2020) which also found out that instructional videos were one of the most accessible media to utilize in teaching in this new normal. Their study also affirmed that videos being utilized were self-made videos of the teachers and others are downloaded from the internet.

Innovations on the Internet and Technology

Teachers shared being that technology savvy was an edge for a teacher to deliver the lesson in this new normal. The teaching in the new normal involved gadgets, platforms and LMS already and it was necessary that a teacher was acquainted with these tools. Technology-based teaching helped the teacher to interact with their students and cope the challenges in remote teaching. The informant added that:

“First, the teacher must know how to use technology or must be technology driven. The teacher must be computer savvy. They must know how to empathize with students because it’s not just the teachers who adjusted but also the students.”

The key informant emphasized the importance of empathy towards students. They learned to understand student’s part since according to the one informant, it was not just the teachers

who were struggling, but also the students. Despite the barrier students and teachers, empathy was still being showcased. This statement of informant disagreed to the phenomenological study of pre-service teachers in Spain by Varea & Gonzalez (2020), which found out that empathy was hard to extend in online class. Teachers were struggling in showing their empathy students which was contradicted to the response of the informant of this study. Another informant said that:

“Technology-based teaching. You need to be resourceful also in looking for challenging applications or learning platforms. You need to be smart and active always. Active and smart must be together. You need to be lively so that students will not fall asleep. That is why I always open my camera.”

The informant shared that being active and lively in the class can help you continue with the teaching-learning process although there was a problem in the connectivity. This supported the study of Hebebcı et al (2020), which stated that keeping students active and engage in the process could make the process speedy.

Innovations in Physical and Cognitive Situations

This quaranteaching did not just affected the teachers but also the students and other stakeholders of the academe. That’s why teachers learned to adjust and innovate when it comes to their physical, cognitive social and personal challenges. Different attributes were beneficial to the teaching-learning process and for having a good student-teacher interaction. One informant highlighted that:

“So, based on my experience a teacher needed to have that passion. Passion not just towards your students or anything else but passion on teaching the subject. Passion in handling everything especially in this time of pandemic because it’s not just us who is struggling but also the students.”

The informant shared being passionate despite all the challenges being faced this pandemic was important. Teachers experienced hardships not just on the job, but also in their personal life. Nevertheless, they continued because it was their chosen profession. This statement supported the study of Woods et al (2020). This article showed that being passionate on your work was one of the keys for you to survive this online teaching. Passion towards your profession helped teacher to stay committed on their job. Another teacher shared that:

“We need to have mastery of the skills and correct interpretation of skill so that we can teach them. As much as possible we need to explain thoroughly so that they will understand. That’s what I did I give them examples in order for them to understand the text.”

Teaching online required proper discussion and in-depth instruction for students to be guided in learning and in doing activities. The informant clearly stated it was important that teacher explain further the lessons and as much as possible gave example. This strategy of one the key informant agreed to the study of Varea et al (2020). According to their study direct instruction and demonstration from teachers helped a lot so that students had an easy way of

catching with lessons and in coping up with the difficulties. This teaching style was commonly used by Physical Education teachers in Spain. Another informant also shared that:

“At first it is hard but later on I used to with routine when it comes to conducting classes. We can realize that yes, it’s manageable. All we must do is to find resources so that we can show them the skills. Deep research on the internet so that students acquiring of skill is good.”

The informant shared that it was important to find resources that sufficed the teaching-learning process. Deep research helped teachers and students acquired skills in Physical Education. This agreed to the study of Lu et al (2020) which stated that teachers must always find reliable resources to know how to properly teach PE in the virtual one.

Theme number 2 concluded that though teachers were having a hard time with the new normal, they learned to cope up with this through adapting to the changes and innovating the practices and pedagogies in teaching. These revealed how teachers innovate in order for them to cope up their challenges in teaching Physical Education, monitoring, assessing and giving feedback to students, dealing with the internet and technology and handling physical and social challenges.

To sum up, the experiences of the Tertiary Physical Educators in *quaranteaching* can be classified into two things. These were the negatives and the positive experiences. Teachers encountered positive and negative experiences in teaching Physical Education, assessment, monitoring and giving feedback to students, coping with

the internet and technology and handling challenges on the physical and cognitive aspects.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers concluded that the experiences of Tertiary Physical Education teachers in teaching Physical Education in the quarantine can be described into two general classifications. They experienced difficulties and innovations in terms of teaching the course, assessment, monitoring and giving feedback to students, dealing with the internet and technology and handling personal and cognitive situations.

RECOMMENDATION

It was the researcher’s main intention to have a deeper understanding of the Physical Education teachers in teaching PE in the quarantine. Based on the conclusion, it was recommended that Physical Education teachers must be exposed in pedagogical and technological trainings and seminarworkshops that would improve their teaching pedagogies, professional capabilities and digitalness. In depth training on the utilization of various Learning Management Systems (LMS) and mobile applications must be given priority for the PE teachers to be competent in teaching of Physical Education in the new normal.

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REFERENCES

- Adnan, M. (2020). Online learning amid the COVID-19 pandemic: Students perspectives. *Journal of Pedagogical Sociology and Psychology*, 1(2), 45–51.
- Aktop, A., & Karahan, N. (2012). Physical Education Teacher's Views of Effective Teaching Methods in Physical Education. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 46, 1910–1913.
- Andrade, M. S. (2015). Teaching Online: A Theory-based Approach to Student Success. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 3(5), 1.
- Bensaid, B., & Brahim, T. (2020). COPING WITH COVID-19: Higher Education in the GCC Countries. *ResearchGate*. Published.
- Education International. (2020, March 25). *COVID-19 and its impact on education*.
- Education: From disruption to recovery*. (2020, September 8). UNESCO.
- Erdemir, N., & Yangın Ekşi, G. (2019). The Perceptions of Student Teachers About Using an Online Learning Environment 'Edmodo' in a 'Flipped Classroom.' *SDU International Journal of Educational Studies*, 6(2), 174–186.
- Filiz, B., & Konukman, F. (2020). Teaching Strategies for Physical Education during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Journal of Physical Education, Recreation & Dance*, 91(9), 48–50.
- Garcia, M., & Weiss, E. (2020). COVID-19 and student performance, equity, and U.S. education policy. *Economic Policy Institute*. Published.
- Global recommendations on physical activity for health*. (2010). Global Recommendations on Physical Activity for Health.
- Guidelines for the Prevention, Control and Mitigation of the Spread of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)*. (2020, May 24). CHED.
- Haverback, H. R. (2020). Middle Level Teachers Quarantine, Teach, and Increase Self-Efficacy Beliefs: Using Theory to Build Practice During COVID-19. *Middle Grades Review*, 6(2).
- Hebebcı, M. T., Bertiz, Y., & Alan, S. (2020). Investigation of Views of Students and Teachers on Distance Education Practices during the Coronavirus (COVID-19) Pandemic. *International Journal of Technology in Education and Science*, 4(4), 267–282.
- Jeong, H. C., & So, W. Y. (2020). Difficulties of Online Physical Education Classes in Middle and High School and an Efficient Operation Plan to Address Them. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(19), 7279.
- Khanal, P. (2021). Lived Experience of Online Teaching During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Implications for Curriculum and Teaching. *Interdisciplinary Research in Education*, 5(1–2), 89–102.
- König, J., Jäger-Biela, D. J., & Glutsch, N. (2020). Adapting to online teaching during COVID-19 school closure: teacher education and teacher competence effects among early career teachers in Germany.

- European Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(4), 608–622.
- Liu, W. (2018). Design of a Digital Art Teaching Platform Based on Automatic Recording Technology. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (IJET)*, 13(08), 185.
- Lu, C., Barrett, J., & Lu, O. (2020). Teaching physical education teacher education (PETE) online: Challenges and solutions. *Brock Education Journal*, 29(2), 13.
- Marciaga, O. L. M. (2019). A Phenomenology: Teachers Lived Experiences with Workplace English as a Second Language (ESL) Programs. *ScholarWorks@UARK*.
- Morrow, R., Rodriguez, A. and King, N. (2015). Colaizzi's descriptive phenomenological method. *The Psychologist*, 28(8), 643-644.
- Mercier, K., Centeio, E., Garn, A., Erwin, H., Martinen, R., & Foley, J. (2021). Physical Education Teachers' Experiences With Remote Instruction During the Initial Phase of the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*, 40(2), 337–342.
- Mohamad Nasri, N., Husnin, H., Mahmud, S. N. D., & Halim, L. (2020). Mitigating the COVID-19 pandemic: a snapshot from Malaysia into the coping strategies for pre-service teachers' education. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 46(4), 546–553.
- Morgan, B. M. (2018). The Lived Experience: A Study In Teaching Online. *Contemporary Issues in Education Research (CIER)*, 11(2), 83–88.
- O'Brien, W., Adamakis, M., O'Brien, N., Onofre, M., Martins, J., Dania, A., Makopoulou, K., Herold, F., Ng, K., & Costa, J. (2020). Implications for European Physical Education Teacher Education during the COVID-19 pandemic: a crossinstitutional SWOT analysis. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(4), 503–522.
- Pace, C., Pettit, S., & Barker, K. (2020). Best Practices in Middle Level Quaranteaching: Strategies, Tips and Resources Amidst COVID-19. *Becoming: Journal of the Georgia Middle School Association*, 31(1).
- Pokhrel, S., & Chhetri, R. (2021). A Literature Review on Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Teaching and Learning. *Higher Education for the Future*, 8(1), 133–141.
- PSC, DepEd agree to include PE under 'new normal.'* (2020, May 28). Philippine News Agency.
- Raiola, G., & Di Domenico, F. (2021). Physical and sports activity during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Physical Education and Sport*. Published.
- Rapanta, C., Botturi, L., Goodyear, P., Guàrdia, L., & Koole, M. (2020). Online University Teaching During and After the Covid-19 Crisis: Refocusing Teacher Presence and Learning Activity. *Postdigital Science and Education*, 2(3), 923–945.
- Rasmitadila, R., Aliyyah, R. R., Rachmadtullah, R., Samsudin, A., Syaodih, E., Nurtanto, M., & Tambunan, A. R. S. (2020). The Perceptions of Primary School Teachers of Online Learning during the COVID-19 Pandemic Period: A Case Study in Indonesia. *Journal of*

- Ethnic and Cultural Studies*, 7(2), 90.
- Sloan, A., & Bowe, B. (2013). Phenomenology and hermeneutic phenomenology: the philosophy, the methodologies, and using hermeneutic phenomenology to investigate lecturers' experiences of curriculum design. *Quality & Quantity*, 48(3), 1291–1303.
- Sari, T., & Nayır, F. (2020). Challenges in Distance Education During the (Covid-19) Pandemic Period. *Qualitative Research in Education*, 9(3), 328.
- Shahidi, S. H., Stewart Williams, J., & Hassani, F. (2020). Physical activity during COVID-19 quarantine. *Acta Paediatrica*, 109(10), 2147–2148.
- Silva-Filho, E., Teixeira, A. L. S., Xavier, J. R. D. S., Braz Júnior, D. D. S., Barbosa, R. A., & Albuquerque, J. A. D. (2020). Physical education role during coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic Physical education and COVID-19. *Motriz: Revista de Educação Física*, 26(2).
- Tartavulea, C. V., Albu, C. N., Albu, N., Dieaconescu, R. I., & Petre, S. (2020). Online Teaching Practices and the Effectiveness of the Educational Process in the Wake of the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Www.Amfiteatrueconomic.Ro*, 22(55), 920.
- THE 1987 CONSTITUTION OF THE REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES – ARTICLE XIV | GOVPH.** (1987). Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines.
- Toquero, C. M. (2020). Challenges and Opportunities for Higher Education amid the COVID-19 Pandemic: The Philippine Context. *Pedagogical Research*, 5(4), em0063.
- Tria, J. Z. (2020). The COVID-19 Pandemic through the Lens of Education in the Philippines: The New Normal. *International Journal of Pedagogical Development and Lifelong Learning*, 1(1), ep2001.
- Varea, V., & González-Calvo, G. (2020). Touchless classes and absent bodies: teaching physical education in times of Covid-19. *Sport, Education and Society*, 1–15.
- Varea, V., González-Calvo, G., & GarcíaMonge, A. (2020). Exploring the changes of physical education in the age of Covid-19. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 1–11.
- Williyanto, S. (2020). The Achievement of Physical Education Learning Objectives during COVID-19 Pandemic. *Proceedings of the 5th International Seminar of Public Health and Education, ISPHE 2020, 22 July 2020, Universitas Negeri Semarang, Semarang, Indonesia*. Published.
- Woods, A., Pettit, S., & Pace, C. (2020). Quaranteaching in the Time of Covid-19: Exemplar From a Middle Grades Virtual Classroom. *Becoming: Journal of the Georgia Middle School Association*, 31(1).